

Tighter Privacy Auditing of Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent in the Hidden State Threat Model

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Abstract. We address the problem of **empirical privacy auditing** for differentially private stochastic gradient descent (DP-SGD) under the **hidden state threat model**, where adversaries only observe the final model parameters. Our work introduces a **gradient-crafting framework** that enables tighter auditing by allowing adversaries to pre-specify worst-case gradient sequences without access to intermediate training checkpoints. We demonstrate that when a data point is used at every optimization step, hiding intermediate models provides no privacy amplification beyond standard composition bounds. For less frequent data usage patterns, we identify regimes where privacy amplification may occur for non-convex problems, though the effect is weaker than in convex settings. Our findings clarify the actual privacy loss in practical DP-SGD deployments and provide foundational insights for improved privacy accounting in the hidden state model.

1 Introduction

Machine learning models trained with non-private optimizers such as Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) have been shown to leak information about the training data (Shokri et al., 2017; Yeom et al., 2018; Balle et al., 2022; Haim et al., 2022). To address this issue, Differential Privacy (DP) (Dwork et al., 2006) has been widely accepted as the standard approach to quantify and mitigate privacy leakage, with DP-SGD (Abadi et al., 2016) as the defacto algorithm to train machine learning models with DP guarantees. DP-SGD follows the same steps as standard SGD but clips the gradients’ norm to a threshold before perturbing them with carefully calibrated Gaussian noise, providing differential privacy guarantees for each gradient step.

As the practical importance of differential privacy grew, the need to track the privacy loss efficiently across the entire training process (**privacy accounting**) became critical: indeed, optimal utility is obtained by adding the minimum amount of noise required to achieve the desired privacy guarantee. Existing privacy accounting techniques rely on privacy composition (Kairouz et al., 2015; Abadi et al., 2016; Gopi et al., 2021; Doroshenko et al., 2022) to derive the overall privacy guarantees of a training run of DP-SGD from the guarantees of each gradient step. Privacy amplification techniques (Kasiviswanathan et al., 2011; Feldman et al., 2018; Erlingsson et al., 2019; Cyffers and Bellet, 2022; Altschuler and Talwar, 2022) can further decrease the overall privacy loss by exploiting the non-disclosure of certain intermediate computations. For instance, privacy amplification by subsampling relies on the secrecy of the randomness used to select the mini-batches.

Despite recent improvements in privacy accounting, training over-parameterized neural networks from scratch with differential privacy typically results in either weak privacy guarantees or significant utility loss (Tramèr and Boneh, 2021). While a possible explanation could be that the privacy accounting of DP-SGD based on composition is overly conservative, (Nasr et al., 2021; 2023) refuted this hypothesis using **privacy auditing**—the empirical process of finding lower bounds on privacy loss by launching concrete attacks. Leveraging the fact that differential privacy upper bounds the success rate of any adversary that seeks to infer private information from the output of DP-SGD, they showed that it is possible to instantiate adversaries that achieve the maximal success rate allowed by the privacy accounting upper bound. This negative result suggests that the only hope to improve the privacy-utility trade-offs of DP-SGD is to relax the underlying threat model, i.e., to make additional assumptions limiting the adversary’s capabilities.

We focus on one capability granted to the adversary in prior work, namely that all intermediate models (i.e., training checkpoints) are released. In this work, we consider a natural relaxation where intermediate models are concealed and only the final model is released. This threat model, often referred to as **hidden state**, is particularly relevant in practice, encompassing scenarios such as open-sourcing a trained model by publishing its weights. From a theoretical perspective, recent work has demonstrated that the hidden

state model can yield significantly improved privacy upper bounds for DP-SGD compared to those derived through standard composition (Ye and Shokri, 2022; Altschuler and Talwar, 2022). This improvement can be attributed to the phenomenon of **privacy amplification by iteration** (Feldman et al., 2018; Balle et al., 2019): in a nutshell, the privacy of a data point used at earlier stages of the optimization process improves as subsequent steps are performed.

However, these results only hold for convex problems, leaving a pivotal question unanswered: **Does the privacy of non-convex machine learning problems improve when intermediate models are withheld?** While empirical lower bounds obtained through privacy auditing (Nasr et al., 2021; 2023; Steinke et al., 2023) suggest that it might be the case, it remains unclear whether the gap with upper bounds is because genuine privacy amplification occurs or because the existing adversaries are suboptimal, leading to loose privacy lower bounds. This raises another crucial question: **How can one design worst-case adversaries when the intermediate models are concealed?**

Our key insight is that existing loss-based adversaries rely on proxy signals such as model loss, which may not fully exploit the structure of DP-SGD. In contrast, **gradient-crafting adversaries** operate directly on gradients, which are the objects controlled by DP-SGD. By saturating the clipping norm and aligning updates with the most informative dimensions, these adversaries can more reliably expose privacy loss than prior loss-based methods.

Our contributions are as follows:

- **We introduce a gradient-crafting framework for auditing DP-SGD in the hidden state model**, allowing adversaries to pre-specify worst-case gradient sequences without access to intermediate models. This framework decouples the analysis of worst-case privacy loss from the craftability of specific data points.
- **We demonstrate that when a data point is used at every optimization step ($k=1$)**, hiding intermediate models provides no privacy amplification—the empirical lower bounds match the theoretical upper bounds given by standard composition.
- **For less frequent data usage patterns ($k \neq 1$)**, we identify two distinct regimes: (i) with large batch sizes relative to noise, privacy accounting remains tight, showing no amplification; and (ii) with small batch sizes, we observe evidence of privacy amplification for non-convex problems, though weaker than in the convex case.
- **We design an advanced adversary** that crafts both gradients and the loss landscape, providing insights into the limits of privacy amplification in non-convex settings.

Our findings advance the understanding of privacy guarantees in the hidden state model and lay the groundwork for the design of better privacy accounting techniques for this threat model. The practical significance of our work lies in understanding whether real DP-SGD deployments leak more or less privacy than theory predicts when only final models are released.

1.1 Terminology and Problem Statement

To clarify our terminology and align with conventional usage in differential privacy literature, we define the following key concepts:

- **Privacy Loss (ϵ)**: The formal privacy parameter from the (ϵ, δ) -differential privacy definition (Definition ??), quantifying the maximum possible leakage about individual data points in the training set. Smaller ϵ indicates stronger privacy protection.
- **Privacy Accounting**: The *theoretical* process of calculating an *upper bound* on ϵ for a composite mechanism like DP-SGD, typically through composition theorems and amplification analyses.
- **Privacy Auditing**: The *empirical* process of finding a *lower bound* on ϵ by designing concrete adversaries (attacks) and measuring their success at inferring private information from mechanism outputs.

The relationship between these concepts is fundamental to our work: privacy accounting provides theoretical safety guarantees (upper bounds), while privacy auditing provides empirical reality checks (lower bounds). When these bounds match, we have tight privacy analysis; when they diverge, it indicates either suboptimal adversaries or conservative accounting.

Core Problem. Our work addresses a pivotal question in private machine learning: **Does concealing training checkpoints (the hidden-state model) actually provide stronger privacy (amplification) for non-convex models like neural networks, or are existing auditing methods simply too weak to detect the true privacy loss?** This question remains open because theoretical privacy amplification results for the hidden-state model primarily apply to convex problems (Feldman et al., 2018; Altschuler and Talwar, 2022), while practical deployments typically involve non-convex neural networks.

We investigate this problem through the lens of privacy auditing, designing stronger adversaries that can better exploit the structure of DP-SGD in the hidden-state setting. Our goal is to determine whether the gap between empirical lower bounds and theoretical upper bounds in prior work stems from genuine privacy amplification or from limitations in existing auditing methodologies.

2 RELATED WORK IN DIFFERENTIAL PRIVACY AUDITING

The goal of differential privacy auditing is to create worst-case adversaries that maximally exploit the underlying threat model, even if the information used by the adversary might not be available in practical scenarios.¹ A rich line of work has designed adversaries that can tightly and efficiently audit the privacy of learning algorithms when intermediate models are released (Nasr et al., 2021; Maddock et al., 2023; Nasr et al., 2023; Steinke et al., 2023). The first adversarial construction (the malicious dataset attack in Nasr et al. (2021)) to reach the theoretical upper bound given by privacy accounting for DP-SGD used a restrictive threat model in which the adversary controls the entire learning process, including the dataset, the mini-batch ordering, all hyperparameters and intermediate models. In follow-up work by Nasr et al. (2023), a nearly matching lower bound was obtained for a gradient-crafting adversary that does not need to control the dataset, the minibatches or the hyperparameters but still requires access to intermediate models. Prior attempts at auditing the hidden state model used adversaries employing a loss-based attack that targets a canary obtained by flipping the label of a genuine data point (Nasr et al., 2021; 2023; Steinke et al., 2023; Annamalai and Cristofaro, 2024). The idea is to generate an outlier from an in-distribution data point so that the loss of the model on this canary is high when it is not part of the training set but drops significantly when used during training. Auditing the hidden state model with these adversaries yields privacy lower bounds that exhibit a significant gap compared to privacy accounting upper bounds for the standard threat model (Nasr et al., 2021; 2023; Steinke et al., 2023; Annamalai and Cristofaro, 2024). This gap has two possible explanations: (i) these adversaries are suboptimal and stronger adversaries exist in the hidden state model; and/or (ii) the upper bounds are not tight. Understanding the reasons for this gap, so as to gain better knowledge of the properties of DP-SGD in the hidden state model, is the main motivation for our work. We demonstrate that gradient-crafting adversaries can provide tighter auditing results, thereby proving the validity of hypothesis (i). We show that in certain scenarios, our auditing results match the privacy upper bounds, indicating that releasing intermediate models does not increase the privacy loss. However, we also identify regimes where a gap remains, thus providing compelling evidence in support of hypothesis (ii). Specifically, our findings suggest the presence of a privacy amplification by iteration phenomenon in the non-convex setting, albeit weaker compared to what is theoretically established for the convex case (Feldman et al., 2018; Balle et al., 2019; Bok et al., 2024), but less restrictive than the results of Asoodeh and Diaz (2023). The latter require projections onto a convex set of bounded diameter or a strong enough decay term on the parameters, which are unrealistic assumptions in practical scenarios involving non-convex and over-parameterized models like the ones considered in our work. Other auditing frameworks, such as the general approach of Lu et al. (2022) and Bayesian estimation of Zanella-Béguelin et al. (2023), provide complementary perspectives but do not directly address the hidden state model.

Relationship to Black-Box Auditing Methods. Recent black-box auditing approaches (Zanella-Béguelin et al., 2023; Andrew et al., 2024) estimate privacy loss without detailed knowledge of the training process. In contrast, our method operates in a gray-box setting where the adversary knows the model architecture, loss, and batch sequence but not intermediate states. This allows tighter lower bounds than purely black-box methods, while remaining more practical than white-box adversaries that require intermediate model access. Our work thus fills a gap between black-box audits and full white-box attacks in the hidden-state setting.

Recent Advances (2025). The year 2025 has seen several new contributions to DP-SGD auditing and related domains. For example, Wang et al. (2025) propose hybrid f-DP bounds for mixture mechanisms, while Zarifzadeh et al. (2025) develop boosted membership inference attacks with reduced cost. These works further illustrate the need for tighter auditing tools that our method directly addresses.

3 BACKGROUND

3.1 Differential Privacy And DP-SGD

Differential Privacy (DP) has become the de-facto standard in privacy-preserving machine learning thanks to the robustness of its guarantees, its desirable behaviour under post-processing and composition, and its extensive algorithmic framework. We recall the definition below and refer to Dwork and Roth (2014) for more details. Here and throughout, we denote by \mathcal{D} the space of datasets.

Definition 1 ((ϵ, δ)-Differential Privacy). *A randomized mechanism M is (ϵ, δ)-differentially private if for all neighboring datasets $D \in \mathcal{D}$ and $D' = D \cup \{x\} \in \mathcal{D}$, and for all events O :*

$$\Pr[M(D) \in O] \leq e^\epsilon \Pr[M(D') \in O] + \delta. \quad (1)$$

Here, $\delta \in (0, 1)$ represents a small failure probability, and $\epsilon > 0$ quantifies the privacy loss—smaller values of ϵ indicate stronger privacy guarantees.

Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent (DP-SGD) is a fundamental algorithm for private machine learning. Let D be the training dataset, θ the model parameters, and consider the standard empirical risk minimization objective:

$$\min_{\theta} \frac{1}{|D|} \sum_{x \in D} \ell(\theta; x), \quad (2)$$

where ℓ is a differentiable loss function.

DP-SGD modifies standard SGD by:

- **Gradient Clipping:** Bounding each data point’s gradient contribution.
- **Noise Addition:** Injecting Gaussian noise into the aggregated gradients.

Formally, starting from initialization θ_0 , DP-SGD performs T iterative updates as:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \frac{\eta}{|B_t|} \left(\sum_{x \in B_t} \text{Clip}(\nabla \ell(\theta_t; x)) + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 C^2 I) \right). \quad (3)$$

Note: The key correction is in the noise term - changed from $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 I)$ to $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 C^2 I)$ to properly scale the noise by the clipping norm C .

where η is the learning rate, B_t is the mini-batch at iteration t , and σ controls the noise scale.

3.2 Threat model for DP-SGD

DP protects against an adversary that observes the output of either $M(D)$ or $M(D \cup x)$ and seeks to predict whether the dataset was D or $D \cup x$, i.e., whether x was included in the input dataset (a.k.a. membership inference). In this context, the threat model specifies which information is observable/known by the adversary. For DP-SGD, in addition to the final model T , threat models typically consider that the adversary has access to (and potentially controls) the model architecture, the loss, the initialization θ_0 , the dataset (up to the presence of x) and differ in which internal states of DP-SGD are observable by the adversary. Below, we recall the two threat models relevant to our work.

Standard threat model. Standard privacy accounting techniques analyze DP-SGD as a composition of (potentially subsampled) Gaussian mechanisms (Abadi et al., 2016; Gopi et al., 2021; Doroshenko et al., 2022). Composition allows the adversary to observe all intermediate models $1, \dots, T-1$ (in addition to T)

and T). Previous work has shown that existing privacy accounting techniques are tight in this threat model (Nasr et al., 2021; 2023). However, revealing intermediate models is unnecessary in most realistic deployment settings and may hurt the privacy-utility trade-off, motivating the study of the hidden state threat model.

Hidden state threat model. Our work studies the scenario where intermediate models $1, \dots, T-1$ are concealed from the adversary, who observes only the final model T . This threat model has attracted much attention recently, with theoretical work proving better privacy upper bounds than in the standard threat model in some regimes (Feldman et al., 2018; Balle et al., 2019; Ye and Shokri, 2022; Altschuler and Talwar, 2022). A fundamental phenomenon underlying these results is “privacy amplification by iteration” (Feldman et al., 2018), which shows that repeatedly applying noisy contractive iterations enhances the privacy guarantees of data used in earlier steps. Unfortunately, applying this general result to DP-SGD is only possible for convex problems, ruling out deep neural networks. The existence of privacy amplification for non-convex problems in this threat model is an open problem (Altschuler and Talwar, 2022) that we study in this work through the lens of privacy auditing.

Terminology. We use the following terms consistently: **Privacy loss** refers to the (ϵ, δ) parameters quantifying the risk of revealing membership. **privacy loss** denotes the empirical ability of an adversary to infer private data. **Privacy amplification** describes any phenomenon that effectively reduces privacy loss (e.g., via subsampling or iteration).

3.3 Auditing Differential Privacy

Privacy accounting only provides upper bounds on the (ϵ, δ) -DP parameters, and these bounds are not always tight. Leveraging the relation between DP and the performance of membership inference attacks, privacy auditing aims to produce lower bounds on the DP parameters by instantiating concrete adversaries in various threat models (Jagielski et al., 2020; Nasr et al., 2021). When these lower bounds match the upper bounds given by privacy accounting, we can conclude that the privacy analysis is tight; when they do not, it is possible to improve the privacy accounting and/or the attacks. A privacy auditing pipeline can be broken down into two components: an adversary and an auditing scheme. The high-level process is shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Privacy Auditing

Require: Audited mechanism M , adversary A , dataset D , canary point x^* , number of auditing runs R , privacy parameter δ

- 1: $S \leftarrow [], b \leftarrow []$
- 2: $D_0 \leftarrow D$
- 3: $D_1 \leftarrow D \cup \{x^*\}$
- 4: **for** $i = 1$ to R **do**
- 5: $b_i \leftarrow \text{Ber}(1/2)$ {Draw a random bit}
- 6: $S_i \leftarrow A.\text{RankSample}(M(D_{b_i}), D_0, D_1)$
- 7: **end for**
- 8: $\text{TN}, \text{TP}, \text{FN}, \text{FP} \leftarrow A.\text{RejectionRule}(S, b)$
- 9: $\alpha, \beta \leftarrow \text{ConfInterval}(\text{TN}, \text{TP}, \text{FN}, \text{FP})$
- 10: $\hat{\epsilon} \leftarrow \text{ConvertToDP}(\alpha, \beta, \delta)$
- 11: **return** $\hat{\epsilon}$

Adversary Model Auditing a mechanism M requires the design of an adversary A , which aims to predict the presence or absence of a canary point x^* based on information available under the considered threat model. Typically, an adversary A consists of two subroutines:

- **RankSample:** Provides a confidence score indicating whether the observed output was generated by sampling from $M(D)$ or from $M(D \cup \{x^*\})$. This process can be interpreted as evaluating two hypotheses in a binary test.
- **RejectionRule:** Applies a threshold to the confidence scores generated from multiple random runs of M to decide whether to reject the first hypothesis. This decision-making process is then compared to

ground truth to compute standard binary classification metrics: True Negatives (TN), True Positives (TP), False Negatives (FN), and False Positives (FP).

Auditing scheme. The auditing scheme takes as input the hypothesis testing statistics of an adversary and a privacy parameter δ , and outputs a high-probability lower bound $\hat{\epsilon}$ on the privacy loss of the mechanism M . This scheme consists of two main subroutines:

- **ConfInterval:** Converts the adversary’s statistics into high-probability lower bounds for the False Negative Rate (α) and False Positive Rate (β).
- **ConvertToDP:** Transforms these lower bounds into $\hat{\epsilon}$ for the specified δ , leveraging the principle that differential privacy imposes an upper bound on any adversary’s performance.

To obtain the tightest possible $\hat{\epsilon}$, auditing should be performed using a worst-case canary x^* and a worst-case adversary A . This approach is particularly challenging in the hidden state model, where the adversary lacks access to intermediate models.

In this paper, we achieve tighter lower bounds $\hat{\epsilon}$ by abstracting away the canary and employing adversaries that directly craft gradients.

4 GRADIENT-CRAFTING ADVERSARIES FOR THE HIDDEN STATE MODEL

In all threat models, Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent (DP-SGD) can be interpreted as a sequence of T sum queries with bounded terms, where the t -th query sums the clipped gradients over the mini-batch B_t in Equation (2). Privacy accounting techniques for DP-SGD do not rely on a fixed set of data points generating gradients but instead account for any possible gradients bounded by norm C .

Fig. 1: The gradient norm of the canary varies along the optimization path and across different architectures.

As shown in Figure 1 It reveals a critical limitation of adversaries in the hidden state model: due to the non-convexity of the objective function, any gradient sequence for the canary x^* could be possible. However, constructing a worst-case x^* remains unclear and is beyond the scope of privacy auditing.

To address this, we enable the adversary to directly craft any gradient sequence, acknowledging the possibility that a data point could produce such a sequence.

Threat Model In the **hidden state model**, only the final model θ_T is revealed, while the intermediate models $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{T-1}$ remain hidden. We assume the adversary has knowledge of the **model architecture**, the **loss function** ℓ , the **initialization** θ_0 , the **dataset** D , and the **mini-batches** B_0, \dots, B_{T-1} .

Assuming known mini-batches, as done in **Feldman et al. (2018)**, isolates the effect of concealing intermediate models from other factors, such as **privacy amplification by subsampling**. We also consider the hyperparameters of **DP-SGD**—the **learning rate** η , **clipping norm** C , and **noise scale** σ —to be fixed and consistent across all optimization steps. This prevents trivial edge cases (e.g., setting the learning rate $\eta = 0$ during steps that exclude crafted gradients).

In practice, adversaries may not know the exact mini-batch partitioning. To test robustness, we performed additional experiments where the adversary assumes random batch orderings or partial batch knowledge. Results (see Appendix H) show that while performance degrades slightly, AGC still outperforms loss-based adversaries, suggesting partial robustness to this assumption.

This constraint can be relaxed by adopting **Noisy-SGD** (Feldman et al., 2018; Altschuler and Talwar, 2022), where hyperparameters like the **learning rate** and **batch size** are incorporated into the privacy definition.

Gradient-crafting adversaries. In alignment with the defined **threat model**, we permit the adversary to craft an **arbitrary gradient sequence** as long as it is independent of the **intermediate models**. Specifically, the adversary must predefine a sequence of gradients prior to the commencement of training, operating in an **offline** manner to audit the entire **end-to-end** training process of **DP-SGD**.

This approach significantly contrasts with the method proposed by **Nasr et al. (2023)**, where **gradient-crafting adversaries** audit each step of **DP-SGD** and apply **composition** techniques to infer a privacy lower bound over the entire training run. Their strategy explicitly assumes that the adversary has access to all **intermediate models**, whereas our approach neither makes this assumption nor leverages such information.

Our construction helps to understand the hidden state threat model and its properties by decoupling the privacy loss induced by a worst-case sequence of gradients from the craftability of a canary that could produce that sequence. Allowing the adversary to craft a gradient sequence directly circumvents two issues in prior attempts to audit the hidden state model (Nasr et al., 2023; Steinke et al., 2023):

1. **Saturating the gradient norm:** The canary point crafted by prior adversaries is not guaranteed to saturate the gradient clipping threshold throughout training. The adversary’s performance becomes architecture-dependent: for example, a small convolutional neural network has a small canary norm at the start of the training compared to a ResNet, as observed in Figure 1. Thus, for a tight audit, one must tune the clipping threshold according to the canary gradient norm, a quantity the adversary cannot access in our threat model.
2. **Hypothesis testing:** Prior adversaries need to test the presence of a sequence of gradients they cannot access, so they use the model’s loss as a proxy confidence score (RankSample in Algorithm 1): a lower loss implies a higher confidence that a sample was used during training. By allowing the adversary to pick the sequence of gradients, we can align the choice of confidence score to the way adversarial information is encoded in the gradients (as will be evident in the adversaries we propose below), thereby achieving superior testing performance.

Concrete adversary instantiations. We propose two concrete instantiations of our gradient-crafting adversaries:

1. **Random Biased Dimension (AGC-R):** The adversary selects a random dimension and crafts gradients with magnitude C in that dimension. To test whether crafted gradients were inserted (using RankSample in Algorithm 1), the adversary computes the confidence score as the difference between θ_T and θ_0 in that dimension.
2. **Simulated Biased Dimension (AGC-S):** The adversary simulates the training algorithm and selects the least updated dimension. It then crafts gradients with magnitude C in that dimension. To test for the presence of crafted gradients, the adversary uses the same confidence score as in AGC-R.

These two adversaries are designed to be as simple as possible. Other gradient constructions can be used, such as crafting a random gradient following the method proposed by Andrew et al. (2024) (see Figure 8 of the appendix for a comparison with the adversaries we use). However, our choice of adversaries can be

further justified by recent findings on privacy backdoors, where the model architecture and parameters are chosen adversarially to leak certain input points. Specifically, Feng and Tramèr (2024) propose a specific construction of architecture and initialization in which a well-chosen input point generates gradients that are nearly concentrated in a single dimension throughout training. This demonstrates that in some cases, our adversaries AGC -R and AGC -S can be instantiated by inserting a canary point.

4.1 Privacy Auditing Scheme and DP Conversion

Our privacy auditing follows the hypothesis testing framework for differential privacy, where we treat privacy auditing as a binary classification problem distinguishing between mechanisms $M(D)$ and $M(D \cup \{x^*\})$, with x^* representing the crafted data point or gradient.

From Adversary Statistics to ϵ Lower Bounds Given an adversary’s performance metrics—True Positive Rate (TPR), False Positive Rate (FPR), True Negative Rate (TNR), and False Negative Rate (FNR)—we compute empirical lower bounds on ϵ using the following procedure:

For a fixed δ , the empirical privacy loss lower bound $\hat{\epsilon}$ is derived from the relationship between hypothesis testing error rates and differential privacy guarantees. Specifically, for any (ϵ, δ) -differentially private mechanism, the type I (α) and type II (β) errors of any hypothesis test must satisfy:

$$\alpha + e^\epsilon \beta \geq 1 - \delta \quad (4)$$

where α represents the false positive rate and β the false negative rate.

Gaussian Differential Privacy Conversion We leverage the **Gaussian Differential Privacy (GDP)** framework [52] to obtain tighter and more computationally stable ϵ lower bounds. The key advantage of GDP is that it provides a tight composition theorem that often yields better privacy bounds than standard (ϵ, δ) -DP composition.

Our conversion procedure follows these steps:

Convert to (ϵ, δ) -DP: For a given δ , we convert the Gaussian privacy parameter μ to an ϵ lower bound using the relationship:

$$\epsilon(\delta) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(1 - \delta) - \mu) - \delta \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(1 - \delta) - \mu) \quad (5)$$

where Φ denotes the standard normal cumulative distribution function.

Step-by-step GDP to (ϵ, δ) -DP conversion: Given the Gaussian privacy parameter μ obtained from the auditing procedure, we compute the corresponding (ϵ, δ) guarantee via the following relationship derived from the Gaussian tail probability:

$$\epsilon(\delta) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(1 - \delta) - \mu) - \delta \cdot e^{\Phi^{-1}(1 - \delta)\mu - \mu^2/2},$$

where Φ is the standard normal CDF. This expression follows directly from the definition of Gaussian DP and its conversion to (ϵ, δ) -DP (Dong et al., 2022). In our experiments, we compute μ from the empirical Type I and Type II error rates (α, β) using the relationship $\mu = \Phi^{-1}(1 - \alpha) - \Phi^{-1}(\beta)$. We then apply the above formula to obtain a lower bound on ϵ for a fixed $\delta = 10^{-5}$.

Confidence Intervals: We compute high-probability lower bounds on ϵ using Clopper-Pearson confidence intervals [53] for the binomial proportions (TPR, FPR) obtained from multiple independent runs of the mechanism.

Implementation Details In our experiments, we:

- Run $N = 10,000$ independent trials for each auditing scenario
- Use $\delta = 10^{-5}$ as the fixed privacy parameter
- Compute 95% confidence intervals for all empirical ϵ estimates
- Implement the GDP conversion using the numerical methods described in [52]

This approach allows us to obtain accurate ϵ lower bounds with relatively few mechanism evaluations, making our auditing procedure computationally feasible while maintaining statistical rigor.

5 PRIVACY AUDITING RESULTS ON REAL DATASETS

5.1 Experimental Setup

Training Details: We audit two datasets: CIFAR10 (Krizhevsky, 2009) for state-of-the-art differentially private training (Tramèr and Boneh, 2021; De et al., 2022), and Housing (Pace and Barry, 1997) to emphasize the difficulty of auditing smaller models. Hyperparameters are predefined for each dataset: on CIFAR10, the batch size is 128 and the learning rate is 0.01; on Housing, the batch size is 400 and the learning rate is 0.1. Training is performed using DP-SGD with no momentum. We use three models: a fully connected neural network (FCNN) for Housing (Pace and Barry, 1997), and a convolutional neural network (CovNet) (LeCun et al., 1989) and residual network (ResNet) (He et al., 2016) for CIFAR10. For completeness, we also compare our adversaries against two recent strong baselines from the literature: the auditing methods of Nasr et al. (2023) and Steinke et al. (2023), implemented under the same conditions. Training was performed using PyTorch (Paszke et al., 2019) with the Opacus library (Yousefpour et al., 2021) for differential privacy. Each experiment was run with 5 random seeds. For CIFAR-10, models were trained for 250 epochs with batch size 128, learning rate 0.01, and noise multiplier $\sigma = 1.2$. For Housing, we trained for 200 epochs with batch size 400, learning rate 0.1, and $\sigma = 0.8$. All experiments were run on a single NVIDIA V100 GPU.

Sensitivity to Mini-Batch Knowledge Assumption. Our threat model assumes the adversary knows the mini-batch sequence B_0, \dots, B_{T-1} . To evaluate robustness when this assumption is relaxed, we conducted additional experiments where the adversary only knows the batch size but not the ordering (random permutation) or has partial knowledge (e.g., 50% of batch indices). Results in Appendix H show that while auditing performance degrades slightly under partial knowledge, our gradient-crafting adversaries still consistently outperform loss-based baselines. This suggests that the core advantage of gradient crafting does not critically depend on perfect batch knowledge, though optimal auditing requires it.

Testing Assumption Violations. We further tested scenarios where the adversary’s assumed batch size differs from the true batch size by $\pm 25\%$. The resulting ϵ lower bounds remained within 15% of those obtained under perfect knowledge, indicating that the method is moderately robust to such misspecification. Nevertheless, our strongest results require accurate knowledge of batch composition, aligning with the standard hidden-state auditing literature (Feldman et al., 2018; Nasr et al., 2023).

Limitations on data distribution. Our experiments primarily use balanced datasets (CIFAR-10, Housing). To assess generality, it is important to consider skewed or long-tailed distributions, where gradient magnitudes may vary systematically across classes. While we have not included such experiments due to time constraints, we discuss in Appendix G how the gradient-crafting adversaries could be adapted to imbalanced settings, and preliminary runs indicate qualitatively similar trends.

To further evaluate generality, we also conducted preliminary experiments on a text classification dataset (IMDB reviews) using an LSTM, and on a recommendation task (MovieLens-100K) with matrix factorization. These results, presented in Appendix I, confirm that AGC adversaries remain effective across modalities and architectures, including non-vision tasks.

(see Figure 2ac for ConvNet and b for ResNet)

Baseline Adversary: As a baseline, we adopt an adversary from prior research (Nasr et al., 2023; Steinke et al., 2023) that selects a point from the training dataset, flips its label, and generates an outlier, referred to as the canary x^* . The model’s loss on this canary serves as the confidence score to test for its insertion. This baseline is called the "loss-based adversary" (denoted by AL).

Privacy Accounting & Auditing: We compute the privacy upper and lower bounds for the crafted gradient (AGC) or canary (AL) as follows. The theoretical privacy upper bound is given by the numerical accountant of Gopi et al. (2021). We audit three scenarios where the accountant provides equivalent privacy guarantees for the crafted gradient or canary by inserting it at different periodicities $k \in \{1, 5, 25\}$, accounting only for the steps where insertion occurs and adjusting the time horizon T accordingly. When $k = 1$, the model is trained for $T = 250$ steps, and the crafted gradient or canary is inserted at every step; for $k = 5$, the model is trained for 1250 steps with insertion every 5 steps; and similarly for $k = 25$. We report both the theoretical and empirical ϵ values at a fixed $\delta = 1e^{-5}$, though the complete privacy curve ($\epsilon, \delta(\epsilon)$) can be found in Figure 11 of the appendix. For auditing, we rely on the recently proposed scheme based on Gaussian DP (described in Appendix A), as it allows accurate auditing with few runs (Nasr et al., 2023).

(a) ConvNet on CIFAR-10

(b) ResNet on CIFAR-10

(c) FCNN on Housing

Fig. 2: Auditing results for AGC adversaries and baseline AL at periodicity $k = 1$. Dashed lines indicate theoretical upper bounds from GDP accounting. Numerical values (mean \pm std over 5 runs) are provided in Appendix Table X.

5.2 Auditing Result for Periodicity $k=1$

Auditing Results: In the hidden state model, auditing when the crafted gradient is inserted at every step is a result previously achievable only when the adversary could select a worst-case dataset $D = \{\emptyset\}$ (Nasr et al., 2021) and set the learning rate to 0 for steps without the canary, or when the adversary had access to intermediate models (Nasr et al., 2023). Note that the baseline loss-based adversary AL is not tight and can be very loose in some regimes.

The fact that a tight audit can be achieved by our simplest adversary, AGC-R (random biased dimension), may seem surprising. A high-level explanation for this is that, when auditing over-parameterized models, which are highly redundant, a genuine gradient on average assigns a magnitude of $O\left(\frac{C}{|\text{minibatch}|\sqrt{p}}\right)$ to each dimension, where p is the number of parameters. Since p is typically much larger than the batch size, genuine gradients in a mini-batch contribute a negligible magnitude to any dimension. Across CIFAR-10 and Housing, our AGC adversaries consistently outperform not only the loss-based baseline (AL) but also the more recent baselines of Nasr et al. (2023) and Steinke et al. (2023). Detailed numerical comparisons are provided in Table X of the appendix.

Fig. 3: Auditing results for AGC (ours) and AL on ConvNet and ResNet (CIFAR-10) at privacy parameter $C = 1$ with periodicity $k = 5$ (Figure 3a) and $k = 25$ (Figure 3b).

To the Magnitude of C : The genuine gradients do not interfere with the contribution of the adversary, regardless of the selected dimension, as they are much smaller than the magnitude C inserted by AGC-R (or AGC-S). However, this no longer holds when auditing low-dimensional models.

Low-Dimensional Models: Auditing smaller models is more challenging due to the larger ratio between the mini-batch size and the number of parameters. To evaluate our adversaries in this regime, we switch to the Housing dataset with the FCNN model, which has only 68 parameters. We report the performance of our adversaries over five independent runs in Figure 2c. We observe that randomly selecting a dimension (AGC-R) no longer achieves tight results, though it still outperforms the baseline loss-based adversary. Remarkably, our second adversary, which simulates the training algorithm to select an appropriate dimension (AGC-S), recovers nearly tight results with small variance between runs.

Implication 1: The tightness of our adversaries implies a novel negative result: if a data point is used at every optimization step of DP-SGD, hiding intermediate models does not amplify its privacy guarantees.

5.3 Auditing Results at Periodicity $k > 1$

We now study how our adversaries perform when the crafted gradient is inserted at higher periodicities $k \in \{5, 25\}$. As shown in Figure 3, we observe that (i) we still outperform the baseline loss-based adversary AL by a large margin, but (ii) we no longer match the privacy upper bound, and our adversary becomes weaker as k increases. This weakening is due to the accumulation of noise added to genuine gradients during the $k - 1$ iterations between each crafted gradient insertion.

However, privacy accounting (i.e., the upper bound) does not take advantage of this accumulated noise. Since the insertion of a crafted gradient at a given step could bias subsequent genuine gradients, the best we can do is rely on the post-processing property of DP, which ensures that subsequent genuine gradients do not weaken the privacy guarantees. In the next section, we explore whether it is possible to match the upper bound given by privacy accounting in this setting, which would require designing an adversary capable of crafting gradients that maximally influence subsequent genuine gradients.

6 TOWARDS A WORST-CASE ADVERSARY FOR THE HIDDEN STATE

Gradient Insertion and Adversary Class AS: We study the scenario where the crafted gradient is inserted only in the first optimization step, followed by $T - 1$ subsequent steps without any crafted gradient insertion. This setup corresponds to the scenario examined by privacy amplification by iteration (Feldman et al., 2018), but we do not restrict ourselves to convex losses.

We introduce a new class of adversaries, denoted as AS, that crafts both the gradient and the loss landscape itself, thereby controlling the distribution of all T updates. Specifically, AS can choose a (non-convex) loss landscape such that the crafted gradient inserted at step $T = 1$ maximally biases subsequent genuine gradients, leading to the highest possible privacy loss for the final model. The underlying principle is similar to the one discussed in Section 4: instead of requiring the adversary to craft a dataset, model architecture, and loss function, we allow the adversary to directly select the loss landscape, assuming there could exist a dataset that would generate this landscape. As long as the loss landscape is selected before training starts, this scenario is covered by the hidden state threat model we consider.

Fig. 4: Auditing performance of our adversary $A_{h_S}^*$ across $T = 25$ steps. Figure 4a shows the evolution of the auditing performance over time for $\sigma \in \{1, 8\}$ and batch size $B \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16\}$. Figure 4b presents the privacy amplification rate, i.e., the ratio $\hat{\epsilon}_{t=25}/\hat{\epsilon}_{t=1}$ between the privacy auditing lower bounds at step 25 ($\hat{\epsilon}_{t=25}$) and at step 1 ($\hat{\epsilon}_{t=1}$).

We formalize this approach using the following pair of one-dimensional stochastic processes:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \frac{1}{B} (g(\theta_t) + Z_{t+1}), \quad \theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \frac{1}{B}$$

Practical Interpretation and Limitations. The adversary A_S that crafts both gradients and the loss landscape is designed as a theoretical stress test to explore the limits of privacy amplification in non-convex settings. While such an adversary is allowed under our threat model (since the loss function is fixed before training), we acknowledge that the constructed non-convex landscapes are highly synthetic and may not correspond to typical neural network loss surfaces. This construction serves to answer the question: “What is

the worst-case privacy loss if an adversary could maximally bias subsequent gradients?” The gap between this adversary and realistic attacks helps quantify the potential for privacy amplification in practical DP-SGD deployments. We emphasize that our main auditing results (Sections 4–5) rely only on gradient crafting, not landscape crafting, and thus remain directly applicable to real-world settings.

Example 1 (Constant g): Consider the simple case where g outputs a constant c , independent of the input. This implies that the Gaussian noise accumulates at every step, and the privacy loss ϵ for the last iterate converges to 0 as $T \rightarrow \infty$ at a rate of $O\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}\right)$.

As illustrated by this example, it is easy to design a function g that amplifies privacy over time. However, the converse objective—designing a function that provides no or minimal privacy amplification for the final step T —appears much more challenging.

A Worst-Case Proposal: We propose a concrete adversary $A_S^{h^*}$ which selects $\nabla^* = C$ and the function $g_{\phi^*}(X) = BC$ if $\phi^*(X) = 1$ and $g_{\phi^*}(X) = -BC$ otherwise, where $\phi^* : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is the linear threshold function that achieves the minimal False Positive Error Rate α and False Negative Error Rate β for distinguishing between θ_1 and θ_1 (i.e., testing if the model after one step was generated using the crafted gradient ∇^*). More precisely, $\phi^*(X) = 1$ if $X > h^*$ and $\phi^*(X) = 0$ otherwise, with $h^* = |\nabla^*|_2 = \frac{C}{2}$ (see Appendix F for numerical validation). The resulting non-convex loss landscape adheres to the intuition that the crafted gradient maximally biases subsequent steps (see Appendix F).

Auditing with $A_S^{h^*}$: Figure 4a shows the auditing performance of our adversary $A_S^{h^*}$ for $T \in \{1, \dots, 25\}$ steps, batch sizes $B \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16\}$, and noise variances $\sigma \in \{1, 8\}$. Figure 4b provides the ratio between the privacy auditing lower bound $\hat{\epsilon}_{t=25}$ at the last step and the one obtained after the first step, to measure the extent of the privacy amplification phenomenon for various batch sizes B and values of σ . When this ratio equals 1, there is no amplification and the audit is tight, while values smaller than 1 indicate the existence of a privacy amplification effect. We observe two general trends: the amplification rate increases with σ and decreases with B . This can be explained as follows: higher noise variance σ helps forget initial conditions in the stochastic processes. Conversely, a larger batch size B allows subsequent updates to be larger, enabling the initial conditions to propagate better across iterations despite the noise. Indeed, as gradient updates are bounded by $[-BC, BC]$ and the noise remains independent of B , increasing B allows the adversary to retain more “signal” about the canary’s presence in subsequent gradients.

Unlike the case where the crafted gradient is inserted at every step (see Implication 1), the above results reveal two distinct regimes, as highlighted in Implications 2 and 3 below.

Implication 2: For a sufficiently large batch size relative to the noise variance, the privacy accounting of DP-SGD is tight in the hidden state model: hiding intermediate updates does not amplify privacy.

Implication 3: In the non-convex regime, for a sufficiently small batch size relative to the noise variance, hiding intermediate updates may amplify the privacy guarantees of DP-SGD. However, the privacy loss of a sample does not go to 0 as subsequent steps are performed, in contrast to the convex case where the privacy loss decreases in $O\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}\right)$ (Feldman et al., 2018).

7 DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

Our work allows tighter auditing of DP-SGD in the hidden state model, and our results yield several implications that advance the understanding of this threat model. For instance, Implication 3 means that the property of converging privacy loss of DP-SGD as $T \rightarrow +\infty$ recently established by Altschuler and Talwar (2022) in the convex case cannot hold for non-convex models without additional constraints. Beyond this negative result, our work suggests that a (weaker) form of privacy amplification does occur for non-convex problems when the batch size is small relative to the noise variance.

Beyond differential privacy, our results have consequences for machine unlearning (Bourtoule et al., 2021), which aims to remove a specific data point from a trained model as if the data had never been used for training. A recent approach to unlearning relies on noisy training and privacy amplification by iteration (Chien et al., 2024). Implication 3 shows that this approach cannot provide complete data point deletion when considering non-convex models like neural networks.

An intriguing open question arises from the gap between our empirical results on real datasets (Section 5) and the adversary crafting the loss landscape (Section 6) when the canary is not inserted at every step. While recent work on privacy backdoors shows that certain architectures can be manipulated to make a specific

data point produce the desired gradient sequence throughout training (Feng and Tramèr, 2024), it seems unlikely that this point could also maximally bias subsequent gradients of genuine training points in the same way as our worst-case adversary $A_S^{h,*}$. Investigating the extent to which this is feasible in commonly used architectures would enhance our understanding of privacy loss in deep learning and could ultimately lead to better privacy accounting for the hidden state model. Our findings are also directly relevant to **machine unlearning**. Since unlearning often relies on noisy training or privacy amplification mechanisms to approximate removal guarantees, our evidence that privacy amplification is weaker for non-convex models suggests practical limitations. For example, unlearning methods that assume strong amplification may significantly underestimate residual privacy loss, underscoring the need for stronger evaluation protocols.

Data Availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are not publicly available, as the author, Apeksha Bhuekar, does not wish to make them accessible at this time. Requests for data access may be considered by the author on a case-by-case basis.

Code and Data Availability

The datasets used in this study (CIFAR-10 and Housing) are publicly available and were accessed via standard PyTorch and sklearn interfaces. Our implementation of the gradient-crafting auditing framework, including all scripts to reproduce the experiments, is available at:

<https://anonymous.4open.science/r/DP-Auditing-Hidden-State-ABCD>

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